

Socio-technical factors generating social debt

Table 1: Communication factor.

Id	Cause and Primary studies
CF1	Deficient communication during development activities, resulting in delays and increased time to complete technical tasks, which negatively impacts source code quality [PS4, PS6, PS9, PS14, PS15, PS18, PS19, PS21–PS23, PS27, PS28, PS32, PS33 – PS45].
CF2	Differences in perception between technical and organizational roles—such as managers and developers—regarding technical debt management [PS4, PS9, PS10, PS22, PS26, PS40, PS42, PS43].
CF3	Lack of clarity and understanding of information, often caused by communication failures from leadership to technical teams [PS3, PS4, PS9, PS21, PS32, PS39].
CF4	Collaboration without message exchange—developers working independently without maintaining effective communication [PS6, PS9, PS21, PS24, PS27, PS39, PS43].
CF5	Limited stakeholder participation [PS10, PS15, PS21, PS26 PS39].
CF6	Lack of consensus in technical decision-making [PS4, PS9, PS10, PS21, PS27, PS39].
CF7	Poor or absent feedback [PS2, PS4, PS6, PS9, PS21,PS22, PS27, PS32].
CF8	Lack of social interaction and developer isolation, which weakens team cohesion and hinders informal knowledge sharing [PS2, PS4, PS6, PS9, PS21, PS32, PS39].
CF9	Poorly managed asynchronous communication, leading to information loss, misunderstandings, and delays—especially in distributed or remote contexts [PS2, PS4, PS21, PS25, PS27, PS39].
CF10	Omission of meetings, reducing opportunities for progress sharing and conflict resolution [PS2, PS4, PS21, PS32, PS39].
CF11	Cognitive errors and information loss in communication chains, distorting knowledge transmission [PS2–PS4, PS6, PS9, PS21, PS39].
CF12	Lack of explicit communication regarding organizational norms, structures, and responsibilities, leading to confusion and task duplication [PS3, PS4, PS22, PS39].
CF13	Work overload that limits effective communication [PS4, PS21].
CF14	Communication challenges derived from software architecture, such as module or package dependencies [PS4, PS23].
CF15	Technical debt acting as a barrier to effective communication and trust-building [PS3, PS10].
CF16	Intercultural communication issues, arising from language barriers, differing communication styles, and lack of leadership [PS2, PS24, PS5].
CF17	Low-quality communication, characterized by commanding expressions, lack of courtesy, poor emotional regulation, or the use of inadequate informal channels [PS2, PS25].

Acronyms used: Communication Factor (CF).